

THE ORGANIZATION OF TEACHING AND LEARNING

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Annotation: The article describes the pedagogical and didactic requirements and effectiveness of education, as the rules for organizing educational activities. Comprehensive human development through the system of continuous education. A person acts as a consumer and producer of educational services in lifelong education and training. Arming all subject teachers with new pedagogical technologies and interactive methods, continuous improvement of skills and application of acquired knowledge in educational activities.

Key words: effectiveness of education, effectiveness of independent work, formation of pedagogical skills, professional thinking, understanding of socio-economic, political, humanitarian knowledge.

The future of each society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is its integral part and a vital necessity. Today, reforming and improving the education system of our country, which is developing in all directions, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing modernity in the use of advanced pedagogical and information technologies, increasing the efficiency of education to the level of meeting global requirements should be the goal of every teacher. The general pedagogical and didactic requirement at all stages of training is to increase the efficiency of independent work based on knowledge, imagination and skills, increase interest in scientific thinking and academic subjects, deepen

professional knowledge, increase activity during training, theoretical and practical preparation.

World pedagogical experience confirms that the possibilities of modern pedagogical technologies to increase interest in subjects and increase their activity in independent work are limitless.

Today, an important condition for its development is the implementation of an improved system of training personnel with modern knowledge, creativity and communication.[1]

To improve the effectiveness of education, to ensure that education is people-centred, and to ensure self-directed learning among young people, educational institutions need teachers who are well trained and who, in addition to in-depth knowledge of their field, are proficient in modern teaching technologies and interactive methods, and are knowledgeable about rules for their use in organizing educational activities. To do this, it is necessary to equip all subject teachers with new pedagogical technologies and interactive methods, and constantly improve their skills in applying acquired knowledge in educational activities. State policy in the field of personnel training provides for the comprehensive development of a person through a system of continuous education. A person acts as a consumer and producer of educational services in lifelong education and training.[2,3]

Young teachers must acquire the necessary pedagogical knowledge of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, technology and teaching methods as they enter the educational process, in addition to their existing knowledge in the specialty. Taking this into account, the main issues in the training of young teachers are determined as follows:

- formation of pedagogical skills that ensure the effectiveness of the educational process;

- formation of new professional thinking aimed at understanding socio-economic, political, humanitarian knowledge;
- mastery of the system of pedagogical knowledge as a methodological basis for the teacher's activities;
- mastery of teaching technology as a system of methods closer to the professional activities of a teacher.

This program was developed with the aim of developing the above qualifications and skills among young talented teachers and scientific personnel currently working in educational institutions.[2,4]

This is teaching modern pedagogical technologies to young talented and promising teachers working in our educational institutions, further strengthening their knowledge of pedagogy and psychology, teaching them how to apply the acquired knowledge in the educational process, as well as revealing to them the secrets of pedagogical skill.

Each teacher can change the methodology of the educational process using technology, based on the content, purpose, as well as the conditions, capabilities and needs of the subject and the subject that he teaches, or create and use his own technologies, based on the technology presented in the educational process.[1 ,5]

In this process, he creates conditions for the development, formation, education and training of the individual and the team, while simultaneously performing the function of management and leadership.

To solve the problems facing the education system in the innovative events that have occurred in the current period, it is necessary to have independent and free-thinking individuals who can assimilate new information and independently evaluate the knowledge gained.

Therefore, the role and importance of modern teaching methods - interactive methods, and innovative technologies in the educational process of educational

institutions are incomparable. Pedagogical technologies, knowledge, and experience of their use in education ensure that students have knowledge and mature skills.

References:

1. Селевко Г. К. Современные образовательные технологии: Учебное пособие. М.: Народное образование, 1998. - С. -5.

2. Суртаева Н. Н. Проектирование педагогических технологий в профессиональной подготовке учителя (на примере естественно-научных дисциплин): Дис... докт. пед. наук. - М., 1995. - С. 219 - 225.

3. Abdulazizovna, K. B. (2022). The use of interactive methods and innovative technologies in entomology lessons while studying insect morphology. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(09), 113-117.

4. Abdulazizovna, K. B., & Rustamjanovna, Z. N. (2022). Education and personality in the context of globalization. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(09), 21-26.

5. Khalilova, B., & Abdurakhmonov, A. (2022). The need to develop environmental knowledge. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(6), 119-124.